

Questions corresponding to the online survey of the article “Perceptions regarding open science appraised by editors of scholarly publications published in Spain” submitted to *Learned Publishing*

Block 1 Data related to the journal
Q1 Journal title
Q2 Indicate the ISSN (print version, if applicable)
Q3 Indicate the eISSN
Q4 Indicate the type of journal publisher
University/Research centre
Commercial publisher
Association/Scientific Society/Professional Association/College
Governmental
Foundation
Royal Academy
Q5 Who holds the journal’s copyright?
The publisher
The authors
The Society/ Scientific Association/ Professional Association
Q6 Please indicate the URL of the journal
Q7 What is the discipline of your journal?
Social sciences
Arts and Humanities
Health Sciences
Engineering
Life sciences
Experimental sciences
Mathematics and physical sciences
Q8 What type of content does your journal publish? (multiple)
Book reviews
Conference proceedings
Research articles
Editorials
Data articles
Opinion articles
Letters to the editor
Literature reviews
Clinical Trials
Q9 What was the launching year of the print version? (if applicable)
Q10 What was the launching year of the electronic version of the journal?
Q11 What is your position in the management/editing of the journal?
Editor
Scientific Editor
Copyeditor
Managing editor
Secretary
Editorial board

Q12 How many years do you estimate your involvement with the management/editing of your journal?
Q13 In which functions of scholarly communication do you have experience? (multiple)
Editor
Editorial board
Author (if you have published any research articles during the last 5 years)
Reviewer
Comment 1. Do you have any comments on this section?
Block 2 Open access (OA) issues
Q14 What access model does your journal follow?
Restricted access by subscription
Restricted and free access after a temporary embargo
Restricted and open access for pay-to-publish articles (hybrid model)
Immediate free access to the publication
Q15 Would you rate your journal as open access?
Answer: Yes/No
Q16 Do you allow re-use of papers without contacting the publisher and in a responsible manner? (e.g. deposit in an OA repository)
Answer: Yes/No
Q17 Is your journal indexed in DOAJ?
Answer: Yes/No/Don't know Yes
Q18 Is your journal indexed in SHERPA/ROMEO?
Answer: Yes/No/Don't know
Q19 Does the journal use Creative Commons licenses? If yes, please indicate which one
The journal does not use Creative Commons licenses
Yes, CC BY
Yes, CC BY SA
Yes, CC BY ND
Yes, CC BY NC
Yes, CC BY NC SA
Yes, CC BY NC ND
Q20 What were the criteria for choosing any licence?
Q21 Are authors required to assign copyright on acceptance of the work?
Answer: Yes/No
Q22 To what extent do you agree with the following statement?
Likert scale 1-5: Do not agree at all (1). Disagree (2). Neither agree nor disagree (3). Agree (4). Strongly agree (5)
The current overall system of scholarly communications works well
Making research publications open access should be common scholarly practice
Open peer review should be common scholarly practice
Making research data open access should be common scholarly practice

Q23 To what extent do you agree with the following statements?
Likert scale 1-5: Do not agree at all (1). Disagree (2) Neither agree nor disagree (3). Agree (4). Strongly agree (5)
OA provides immediacy to publications
OA provides transparency in the publication's business model
OA facilitates openness of publications to professionals and society at large
Open Access journals achieve sustainability by charging for APCs
OA increases the visibility of the journal
OA promotes innovation in types of publications and content
OA enables reuse and sharing of content
OA enables compliance with institutional or other open access policies
Open access facilitates the deposit of works elsewhere (IRs...)
Block 2 cont.
Q24 To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding open access to publications?
Likert scale 1-5: Do not agree at all (1). Disagree (2) Neither agree nor disagree (3). Agree (4). Strongly agree (5)
The emergence of predatory journals jeopardises the credibility of open access journals without APCs
New open access journals suffer from delays to entry into recognised databases
The cost of APCs creates economic barriers between scientific communities
Voluntarism of editorial teams threatens the survival of open access journals
Concentration of the publishing market in a few companies hampers competitiveness
Independent journals cannot compete with the management, negotiation and marketing capacity of large publishers.
Comment 2: Do you have any comments on this section?
Block 3 Your journal's evaluation system and your opinion of open peer review (OPR)
Q25 How is the peer review of your journal conducted?
Double-blind system
Single-blind system
Editorial review (internal)
The identity of authors and reviewers is known to each other (open peer review)
Q26 In general, how satisfied are you with the peer review system used by scholarly journals?
Response: Very low. Low. Neither low nor high. Very high. Very high

Q27 There are many ways to modify peer review processes. Here we define some of these innovations. Do you think they will make peer review better, worse or have no effect?
Answer: Much worse. Worse. Neither better nor worse. Better. Much better
Open Reporting: Peer review in which the review reports are published together with the corresponding article
Open Identity: Peer review where authors and reviewers are aware of each other's identity
Open participation: Peer review that allows wider community to contribute to the review process
Open interaction: Peer review that allows and encourages direct reciprocal discussion between the author(s) and reviewers, as well as between reviewers.
Open pre-review manuscripts: Manuscripts are made immediately available (e.g. via preprint servers such as ArXiv) prior to any formal peer review procedure
Open commenting on the final version: Review or comment on the published version of the paper
Open platforms: Peer review unlinked to the venue where it has been published (external review).
Q28 According to any of the above definitions, do you have any personal experience of open peer review?
Yes, as editor
Yes, as author
Yes, as publisher
No experience
Q29 We define "Open Reporting" as peer review in which the review reports are published together with the corresponding article. Have you been involved in a review process with open reporting? How?
Answer: As reviewer/ As author/ None
Q30 Do you use Publons for acknowledgement of reviewers (with consent)?
Yes/No
Q31 To what extent do you agree with the following statements?
Likert scale 1-5: Do not agree at all (1). Disagree (2). Neither agree nor disagree (3). Agree (4). Strongly agree (5)
Everyone with sufficient knowledge should be able to participate in the open review process, regardless their category or area of work
Making the identities of reviewers open will make reviewers less likely to make strong criticisms
Making the identities of reviewers open will increase the quality of reviews
Reviewers should be able to choose whether or not to make their identities public
Making reviewer identities open is fairer to authors
Increased interaction between research teams and reviewers will lead to better publications

Q32 To what extent do you agree with the following statements?
Likert scale 1-5: Do not agree at all (1). Disagree (2) Neither agree nor disagree (3). Agree (4). Strongly agree (5)
Open peer review makes it difficult to find accepting reviewers
Rivalry between peers can slow down open peer review
Open peer review can lead to conflicts of interest among peers
The prestige of the journal may condition whether or not to accept open peer review (bias made by reviewers)
Open peer review would lengthen the review process.
I like to maintain the status quo of the traditional peer review system.
Habits acquired by discipline affect the acceptance of an open peer review system.
Comment 3. Do you have any comments on this section?
Block 4 Editorial policy regarding preprints
Comment Preprints are versions of articles submitted to journals for publication that have not yet gone through the peer review process. This section is concerned with editorial policies regarding preprints and the opinion on the merits of depositing preprints in open access repositories.
Q33 Are you familiar with the term preprints?
Answer: Not at all familiar/ Unfamiliar/ Somewhat familiar/ Familiar/ Very familiar
Q35 Does your journal have an editorial policy regarding preprints?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q36 If you accept preprints, does your journal provide information on where to deposit them?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q37 If you accept preprints in the reference list, does your journal provide information on how to cite them?
Answer: Yes/No
Q38 To what extent do you agree with the following statements?
Likert scale 1-5: Do not agree at all (1). Disagree (2) Neither agree nor disagree (3). Agree (4). Strongly agree (5)
The preprint deposit may lead to confusion about which version to cite
The preprint may be confused with the first online version
Authors fear that preprints may give false positives in the detection of plagiarism
Preprints may accelerate cases of fraud, plagiarism or malpractices
Preprints raise concerns about breaking the journal scoop
Q39 To what extent do you agree with the following statements?
Likert scale 1-5: Do not agree at all (1). Disagree (2). Neither agree nor disagree (3). Agree (4). Strongly agree (5)
At a time of pandemic, preprints have accelerated research progress
Preprints generally accelerate the advancement of scientific communication
Preprints can accelerate peer review prior to formal review
Discipline affects authors' preprint pre-deposit habits
Comment 4. Do you have any comments on this section?
Block 5 Editorial policy on the raw data underlying publications
Q40 Does your journal have an editorial policy on the data underlying published results?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q41 Does the policy require prior deposit of data in a data repository?
Answer: Yes/ No

Q42 Does the policy recommend depositing the data in the own journal?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q43 Does the policy require data to be made available as supplementary material?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q44 Are research data assigned a DOI if deposited with the own journal?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q45 Do authors assign distribution licences to datasets prior to archiving?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q46 Does the journal provide the tool to assign distribution licences to datasets during submission?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q47 Does your journal recommend repositories where to deposit datasets?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q48 Does your journal provide information on how to cite datasets?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q49 Does your journal provide data files to reviewers as supplementary material?
Answer: Yes/ No
Q50 Are the datasets evaluated by the reviewers as part of the article?
Answer: Yes/ No

Q51 To what extent, as editor, do you agree with the following statements?
Open data underlying publications makes it easy for readers to access data files
Open data underlying publications provides reliability and trustworthiness of the journal
Open data underlying publications gives more visibility to results
Open data underlying publications is an indicator of journal quality
Open data underlying publications allows validation of results
Open data underlying publications allows for reuse under the terms of its licence of use
With a data policy the journal contributes to the fulfilment of open research data mandates
Q52 To what extent, as editor, do you agree with the following statements?
Likert scale 1-5: Do not agree at all (1). Disagree (2) Neither agree nor disagree (3). Agree (4). Strongly agree (5)
Open data underlying publications may compromise the exploitation of the data and possible economic interests
Open data underlying publications raises questions about who owns the data and who determines what to do with them
Open data underlying publications can lead to misuse of data
Open data underlying publications can lead to misappropriation of data
Research staff do not know where to deposit their data so that it is findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable
Open data underlying publications creates uncertainty as it is not pre-reviewed
Comment 5: Do you have any comments on this section?